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Abstract

This paper examines the effect of political dissimilarity on the bilateral trade of critical minerals, which are essential for renewable energy and high-technology applications. Using UN voting similarity as a measure of political dissimilarity, we empirically examine how international relations impact trade flows. Moreover, we distinguish between processed and semi-processed goods, between commodities used in energy and digital applications and those not used in these sectors, and between products traded in concentrated versus diversified markets. Employing a gravity model over the period 1995-2022 and the Poisson Pseudo Maximum Likelihood (PPML) estimator, we account for zero trade flows and heteroskedasticity. Our analysis reveals that political dissimilarity with China and the United States is an important determinant of trade in critical minerals, particularly for semi-processed products, those used in energy and digital transitions, and products with more geographically concentrated markets. At the product level, minerals such as nickel, cobalt, vanadium, molybdenum, copper, and aluminum appear especially sensitive to strategic considerations. Finally, our findings are robust across different model specifications, particularly with respect to concerns about endogeneity between political dissimilarity and trade in critical minerals.

Keywords: critical minerals, gravity model, political proximity, institutions

JEL classification: F14, C55, Q34, Q35, Q43.

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Abstract

This paper examines the effect of political dissimilarity on the bilateral trade of critical minerals, which are essential for renewable energy and high-technology applications. Using UN voting similarity as a measure of political dissimilarity, we empirically examine how international relations impact trade flows. Moreover, we distinguish between processed and semi-processed goods, between commodities used in energy and digital applications and those not used in these sectors, and between products traded in concentrated versus diversified markets. Employing a gravity model over the period 1995-2022 and the Poisson Pseudo Maximum Likelihood (PPML) estimator, we account for zero trade flows and heteroskedasticity. Our analysis reveals that political dissimilarity with China and the United States is an important determinant of trade in critical minerals, particularly for semi-processed products, those used in energy and digital transitions, and products with more geographically concentrated markets. At the product level, minerals such as nickel, cobalt, vanadium, molybdenum, copper, and aluminum appear especially sensitive to strategic considerations. Finally, our findings are robust across different model specifications, particularly with respect to concerns about endogeneity between political dissimilarity and trade in critical minerals.

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1. Introduction

In recent years, there has been a growing academic and policy interest in critical minerals such as cobalt, lithium, aluminum, and rare earth elements. With highly concentrated supply chains and exponentially growing demand, countries have become increasingly dependent on trade in these minerals. Indeed, over the past 20 years, annual trade in energy-related critical minerals has surged from US\$53 billion to US\$378 billion (World Trade Organization, 2024), as these resources are indispensable for both national security and economic resilience. Yet, in the current context of geopolitical tensions, trade in general is affected by political considerations (Cai et al., 2024). As countries become more reliant on cross-border mineral flows, the strategic interdependencies created by this trade raise important questions about how geopolitical relations shape access to these essential inputs for the energy transition—particularly since 2017, with the onset of the trade war between China and the United States. Hence, this paper examines the political determinants of trade in critical minerals.

At the demand level, these minerals are essential for the advancement of renewable energy and the electrification of transportation, serving as key components in electric vehicle (EV) batteries and renewable energy installations. Their role in these technologies has driven a rapid increase in global demand. For example, a typical electric vehicle requires six times the mineral input of a conventional internal combustion engine vehicle, while an offshore wind plant requires approximately nine times more mineral resources than a gas-fired power plant (IEA, 2021). As global climate ambitions intensify and the energy transition accelerates, the International Energy Agency (IEA) projects a substantial increase in the demand for critical minerals. In its Announced Pledges Scenario, demand is expected to more than double by 2030, while in a Net Zero Scenario, it could increase more than threefold, exceeding 30 million tonnes by that year (IEA, 2023). Beyond the energy sector, these minerals also play important roles in high-technology and military applications, further underscoring their significance for national security (Eggert, 2010; Vivoda et al., 2025).

At the supply level, critical minerals are highly concentrated geographically, posing challenges distinct from those associated with traditional energy sources such as crude oil or natural gas. In 2020, Australia accounted for nearly 48% of global lithium production, the Republic of Congo held a 67% share of cobalt, and China produced 57% of the world's aluminum (World Mining Data, 2023). This uneven distribution has driven a sharp increase in

international trade to meet growing demand. Clearly, this trade depends on classical economic determinants such as resource endowments, market size, distance, trade agreements, and trade policy (Korinek, 2019). However, given the strategic interdependencies created by trade in critical minerals, understanding the dynamics of these flows requires acknowledging the broader geopolitical landscape in which they occur.

The global supply chain for critical minerals is both an economic and strategic issue, shaped by political alliances, historical ties, and current diplomatic relations. The interdependence created by trading these materials can stabilize or destabilize international relationships. As countries seek access to critical minerals, they must navigate various geopolitical factors. In addition, the concentration of mineral production in a few key regions makes diplomatic and trade relationships with these producers crucial. Geopolitical risk, political stability, and international cooperation significantly influence the availability and price of critical minerals (Saadaoui et al., 2025). As competition for these resources grows, understanding the geopolitical factors that affect trade flows is essential, especially since the beginning of the trade war between the USA and China. In this context, this study aims to answer the following question: *How does political dissimilarity between countries influence the trade of critical minerals?*

In the existing literature, empirical analyses focusing on the determinants of trade in critical minerals are limited and predominantly emphasize economic factors. Utilizing a gravity model, Shigetomi et al. (2017) highlight the significance of economic scale (GDP per capita and population), geographical distance, internet access in importing countries, and industrialization levels in exporting countries in facilitating trade across 231 countries and regions in the year 2005. Similarly, Islam et al. (2024) employ the gravity model to reveal the considerable impact of renewable energy production, exchange rates, and economic growth on Indonesia's mineral exports to 18 leading importing countries, while also identifying an inverse relationship with domestic income levels. Additionally, Wang et al. (2023) investigate trade relations between China and ASEAN countries using a panel Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model, finding that economic size, geographical proximity, and financial market openness positively affect trade volumes, whereas poverty rates and improvements in sustainable development indices have a negative impact. In contrast, the exploration of political determinants in the trade of critical minerals tends to be qualitative and descriptive.

Studies by Vivoda et al. (2024), Kalantzakos (2019), and He (2018) explain the role of international relations, trade alliances, and conflicts in shaping trade in critical minerals.

Against this background, this paper examines the effect of political dissimilarity on bilateral trade in critical minerals, contributing to the literature in three key ways. First, we provide a quantitative assessment of political alignment in trade by using UN voting similarity as a measure of political dissimilarity. Unlike much of the existing literature, which examines political influences qualitatively or through case studies, we apply a systematic measure across countries and over time. In particular, we calculate political dissimilarity with respect to both China and the United States, allowing us to examine how trade in critical minerals responds to alignment with—or distance from—two major geopolitical actors.

Second, we examine how the relationship between political dissimilarity and trade in critical minerals varies across different product characteristics. Specifically, we distinguish between processed and semi-processed goods. From an economic perspective, this differentiation is intuitive as processed minerals, being higher in value and closer to end-use, may be less sensitive to political relations compared to semi-processed minerals, which are still several steps away from final consumption and which are related to factor endowments. Yet, it is worthy to note that processed minerals might be also sensitive, given that most of the processing takes place in China. Moreover, we distinguish between commodities used in energy and digital applications and those not used in these sectors. This helps identify whether political proximity is greater when the demand for critical minerals is stronger or not. Finally, we differentiate between products traded in concentrated versus diversified markets, given that, as it was mentioned before, these minerals are characterized by a high level of concentration. In a nutshell, this disaggregated approach allows us to assess whether the sensitivity of trade to political alignment is stronger for products that are more strategic, technologically relevant, or subject to supply constraints.

Lastly, the analysis uses a gravity model to explain bilateral trade for critical minerals over the period 1995-2022, considering zero trade flows by employing the Poisson Pseudo Maximum Likelihood (PPML) estimator. This methodological approach allows for a more accurate estimation by addressing the common issue of zero trade flows and heteroskedasticity in trade data, especially in trade in critical minerals, which ensures the robustness of the findings.

Our results can be summarized as follows. First, political dissimilarity with China and the United States is an important determinant of trade in critical minerals, particularly for semi-processed products, those used in energy and digital transitions, and products with more geographically concentrated markets. Second, when we compare geopolitical blocs—defined as the East (China and Russia) and the West (the United States, United Kingdom, and France)—the results remain consistent, reinforcing the importance of political factors in shaping trade patterns. Third, at the product level, minerals such as nickel, cobalt, vanadium, molybdenum, copper, and aluminum appear especially sensitive to strategic considerations. Finally, our findings are robust across different model specifications, particularly with respect to concerns about endogeneity between political dissimilarity and trade in critical minerals.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 describes the data sources, key variables, and classification strategies used in the analysis, and presents stylized facts on trade in critical minerals and their relationship with political dissimilarity. Section 3 outlines the methodology, explaining the gravity model and the use of the PPML estimator. Section 4 presents the results of the analysis. Finally, Section 5 offers conclusions, summarizing the findings and their implications.

2. Data and Stylized Facts

The data used in our analysis includes detailed information on critical minerals and political dissimilarity to comprehensively investigate the factors influencing trade in critical minerals. Below, we provide a detailed description of the datasets and variables employed in our study. Tables A.1 and A.2 in the Appendix present the critical minerals data utilized in our analysis, obtained from the UNCOMTRADE-BACI database using the respective HS6 code.

At the international level, trade in critical mineral has significantly increased in recent years. Yet, it did not uniformly increase across different products. Figure 1 shows that, between 2017 and 2022, trade in rhodium increased by 72%, lithium 53% and magnesium 26%, nickel 16%, and copper 12%. The main reason behind this increase is their use in clean energy technologies in a wide range of products (wind turbines, photovoltaic supply chains, batteries, electric cars, etc.).

As it was mentioned before, we argue in the paper that political dissimilarity matters in shaping the pattern of trade in critical minerals. To measure political dissimilarity, being our main independent variable, we use the similarity in United Nations votes between countries,

Figure 1: Growth rate of trade in critical minerals between 2017 and 2022
 Source: Authors' own elaboration using WTO dataset.

based on the dataset from (Voeten, 2009). Specifically, we calculate the political dissimilarity with respect to China and to the USA by determining the similarity of each country's UN votes to those of China and the USA. For each country pair, we take the absolute difference between its vote similarity scores with each of these two countries in a given year. This approach allows us to quantify the political alignment between countries in relation to China and the USA, with smaller absolute differences, indicating lower political dissimilarity (or a higher political proximity). The intuition behind this measurement is that countries with similar voting patterns at the UN are likely to have closer political relations, which can influence their trade dynamics, especially in strategically important sectors like critical minerals. This approach allows us to capture political dissimilarity to both a Western and an Eastern geopolitical power, providing a more comprehensive analysis of the influence of political relations on trade. Throughout our analysis, we distinguish between the period before and after 2016 due to the onset of heightened geopolitical tensions, particularly the trade war initiated by the U.S. administration. Indeed, in the 2016 US presidential election, Trump promised to reduce the US trade deficit with China and in August 2017, the United States Trade Representative (USTR) investigated the different Chinese practices and, following the

publication of the USTR report, Trump ordered the imposition of tariff duties on Chinese products and filed a WTO case against China. Since then, the trade war has been escalating and came back much more intensively in 2025.

Figure 2 provides a comparison of median trade values under different levels of political dissimilarity with China and the United States, split between the periods before and after 2016. Panel 2(a) displays trade values for “low” versus “high” dissimilarity with China, while panel 2(b) does the same for the United States. In each panel, the two bars on the left represent the period before 2016, and the two bars on the right cover the period after 2016. The numeric labels above each bar report the median trade value (in thousand USD), allowing a direct comparison across both time and dissimilarity levels.

In Panel 2(a), products with low dissimilarity to China increased from a median value of 189 thousand USD before 2016 to 204 thousand USD afterward (an increase of about 8%). High-dissimilarity products with China rose from 137 to 140 thousand USD (approximately 2% growth). In Panel 2(b), low-dissimilarity products with the United States increased from 203 to 257 thousand USD (around a 27% rise), while high-dissimilarity products declined from 127 to 117 thousand USD (a decrease of about 8%). Comparing the two panels, the increase in trade for low-dissimilarity products is more pronounced in the U.S. context than in the Chinese context, while high-dissimilarity products show a slight gain when linked to China but a decline when linked to the United States. These results suggest that, after 2016, political alignment — particularly with the United States — became more closely associated with rising trade flows, whereas products that diverge politically from the United States experienced a relative decline.

The previous comparison is conducted at the aggregate level, considering all critical minerals as a single group. However, there may be heterogeneity across products depending on how they are categorized or used. In particular, differences may arise based on the level of processing, whether the minerals are used in energy and digital applications, and the degree of market concentration. Thus, as it was mentioned before, at the processing level, processed minerals, being higher in value and closer to end-use, may be less sensitive to political relations compared to semi-processed minerals, which are still several steps away from final consumption and which are related to factor endowments. However, processed minerals might be also sensitive, given that most of the processing takes place in China. Second, at the demand level, political proximity might matter more when the demand for critical minerals used in the energy and the digital transition is stronger. This is why we distinguish between

Figure 2: Median trade value by political dissimilarity with China and the U.S., before and after 2016
Source: Authors' own elaboration using UNCOMTRADE-BACI and Voeten et al. (2009).

products that are used in both the energy and the digital transition, those used in one of them, and those that are not used in both. Finally, at the supply level, these minerals are characterized by a high level of concentration. This is why we distinguish between minerals sold in concentrated vs. diversified markets. To account for this, the following figures present disaggregated analyses based on these three dimensions: processing stage, application in energy and digital sectors, and supply concentration. The detailed classification indicating which products fall into each category is provided in Tables A.1 and A.2 in the Appendix.

Figure 3 presents four panels, each one plots the median trade value of critical minerals over time, grouped by whether their political positions are classified as having low or high dissimilarity with China (in panels 3(a) and 3(b)) or with the United States (in panels 3(c) and 3(d)). The classification into low and high dissimilarity is based on a threshold that splits products according to how much their voting patterns differ from each partner. The blue line represents products in the low-dissimilarity group, and the red line represents products in the high-dissimilarity group. The panels differ according to whether the minerals are processed (a, c) or semi-processed (b, d). Figure 3(a) shows that, for processed minerals with China, the median trade value of low-dissimilarity products remains above that of high-dissimilarity products in most years. Figure 3(b), which focuses on semi-processed minerals with China, also has low-dissimilarity products trading at higher levels overall, although the gap between the two lines fluctuates more and narrows in certain periods. In Figure 3(c), covering

processed minerals with the United States, the two lines follow a stable pattern in which low-dissimilarity products generally exhibit higher trade values. In contrast, Figure 3(d) addresses semi-processed minerals with the United States and reveals that the red and blue lines often converge, indicating a narrower or more variable difference between the two groups. Thus, overall, comparing processed and semi-processed categories, processed minerals show a clearer and more consistent separation between the low- and high-dissimilarity lines. Semi-processed minerals display more volatility in the gap, suggesting that the influence of political differences on trade values may be less predictable in intermediate stages of production than in more advanced stages. This result is of particular interest given that most of the processing and refining of critical minerals takes place in China (68% of nickel, 40% of copper, 59% of lithium, 73% of cobalt and most of rare earth elements), which makes China the top supplier of processed minerals (Purdy and Castillo, 2022).

Figure 3: Median trade value over time by political dissimilarity and processing stage
Source: Authors' own elaboration using UNCOMTRADE-BACI and Voeten et al. (2009).

Figure 4 presents six sub-figures with each plots the median trade value of critical minerals over time, separating products by whether they are used in both energy and digital applications, used in either energy or digital applications, or used in neither. Within each panel, products are further divided by low or high dissimilarity with China (top row) or the United States (bottom row). In Figure 4(a), covering products used in both energy and digital applications with China, the low-dissimilarity group (blue) generally trades at higher values

than the high-dissimilarity group (red), although the gap widens and narrows over time. Figure 4(b), focusing on products used in either energy or digital applications with China, shows a similar tendency for the low-dissimilarity group to remain above the high-dissimilarity group, but with periods of closer convergence. Figure 4(c), covering products used in neither energy nor digital applications with China, again reveals that the low-dissimilarity group mostly trades at higher levels, with occasional fluctuations in the gap. Figures 4(d), 4(e), and 4(f) provide the same breakdown for dissimilarity with the United States. In panel (d), products used in both energy and digital applications display a stable advantage for the low-dissimilarity group. Panel 4(e), covering either energy or digital applications, exhibits greater year-to-year variation in the distance between the two lines. Figure 4(f), focused on products that are neither energy nor digital, again shows that low-dissimilarity products typically trade at higher values, but the gap is narrower or more volatile over certain periods. Thus, comparing across all sub-figures, products with lower political dissimilarity to either partner tend to record higher trade values, especially for the “both energy & digital” category. Products in the “either” and “neither” categories often show more fluctuation, resulting in a less consistent difference between the low- and high-dissimilarity groups over time. This confirms the fact that political proximity matters for critical minerals that are more demanded at the global level.

Figure 4: Median trade value over time by political dissimilarity and use in energy and digital applications

Source: Authors’ own elaboration using UNCOMTRADE-BACI and Voeten et al. (2009).

Figure 5 reproduces the same figures but grouped by whether they are concentrated or not. Concentration is assessed by a Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI) measure that reflects how much trade is dominated by a small number of suppliers. High HHI scores imply that the products in question rely on fewer, more dominant sources (“concentrated”), whereas lower scores point to a more diversified supply base (“unconcentrated”). The detailed estimation of HHI is provided in the Appendix. These four figures each plot the median trade value of critical minerals over time, split by whether the products are concentrated (left) or unconcentrated (right), and by whether they have low or high political dissimilarity with China (top row) or the United States (bottom row). In Figure (a), covering concentrated products with China, the blue line remains above the red line for most of the period, with the gap widening after 2020. Figure 5(b), which focuses on unconcentrated products with China, exhibits greater volatility, including phases where high-dissimilarity products exceed their low-dissimilarity counterparts. Figures 5(c) and 5(d) repeat this separation for the United States, showing that low-dissimilarity groups (blue) often trade at higher levels than the high-dissimilarity groups (red), though unconcentrated products (Figure 5(d)) display more frequent crossings between the two lines. Therefore, the concentrated category tends to show a clearer and more stable separation between low and high dissimilarity, while unconcentrated products display wider fluctuations over time.

Figure 5: Median trade value over time by political dissimilarity and supply concentration
 Source: Authors’ own elaboration using UNCOMTRADE-BACI and Voeten et al. (2009).

Against this background, the next section empirically tests how political dissimilarity matters for trade in critical minerals.

3. Methodology

The methodology used in this paper relies on the gravity model of international trade (Yotov et al., 2016). We estimate our gravity model using the Poisson Pseudo Maximum Likelihood (PPML) estimator, which has three main advantages. First, it controls for the information contained in the zero bilateral trade observations due to its multiplicative form (Burger et al., 2009). Second, it accounts for potential inconsistencies in the presence of heteroskedasticity, which often plagues trade data. Third, it asserts that the gravity-fixed effects are identical to their structural counterparts (Yotov et al., 2016; Silva and Tenreyro, 2006). Thus, we estimate the following econometric specification:

$$EXP_{kijt} = \exp[\beta_0 + \beta_1 Dissimilarity_{ijt} + \beta_2 Dissimilarity_{ijt} \times Post2016 + \sigma_{it} + \sigma_{jt} + \sigma_{ij}]u_{kijt} \quad (1)$$

where EXP_{kijt} represents the exports of the critical mineral (k) from country (i) to country (j) in time (t), and $Dissimilarity_{ijt}$ is measured by the absolute difference between the country's votes in the UN General Assembly and those of China and those of the United States. Yet, as it was mentioned before, controlling for the start of the trade war in 2017 is crucial as the global economy, since then, witnessed a lot of geopolitical tensions. Thus, we interact political dissimilarity with a dummy variable that takes the value of 1 after 2016 and zero otherwise, $Dissimilarity_{ijt} \times Post2016$. u_{kijt} is the error term.

We control for three fixed effects. σ_{it} and σ_{jt} are exporter-time and importer-time fixed effects that take multilateral resistance into account. σ_{ij} is the pair-fixed effects that are included for two reasons. First, they mitigate the potential endogeneity problem resulting from the unobserved heterogeneity in trade flows or omitted variables with respect to the bilateral variables in the gravity model (Baier and Bergstrand, 2007; Baier et al., 2019). Second, they account for all observable and, more importantly, unobservable time-invariant bilateral trade costs between the trading partners that are included standardly in the gravity model, such as geographical distance, cultural ties, colonial links, and trade restrictions. In this context, Yotov et al. (2016), Egger and Nigai (2015), and Agnosteva et al. (2019) confirm that pair-fixed effects provide more accurate and comprehensive estimates of all bilateral trade costs than the standard set of gravity variables.

Our analysis is extended in several ways. First, we examine the heterogeneous impact of political dissimilarity for different groups of products (by level of processing, concentration, and the use in energy and digital applications). Second, we run individual regressions to analyze the effect on each mineral. Finally, for political dissimilarity, while we distinguish between the USA and China (being the most influential members of the Security Council), we extend this definition to include the Eastern and Western blocs. To do so, we compute two average vote dissimilarity variables to represent each bloc. The Western bloc average includes the absolute differences in vote similarity with the USA, UK, and France, while the Eastern bloc average includes the absolute differences with China and Russia. The intuition behind these aggregated measures is to capture broader political alignment trends within these two major geopolitical groups.

Finally, to test the robustness of our results, we proceed in two ways. First, we run the regressions using trade volumes instead of trade values to remove the price effect. Second, to control for the endogeneity between political dissimilarity and trade in critical minerals, we proceed by first-differencing bilateral trade flows (Wooldridge, 2010). We believe that, in addition to the inclusion of pair-fixed effect, the risk due to endogeneity is reduced (Egger and Nigai, 2015).

4. Empirical results

The results section is structured to systematically explore the impact of political proximity on trade in critical minerals. First, subsection 4.1 presents an aggregated analysis of the effect of political proximity on trade value using a collapsed dataset. Next, in 4.2, we examine disaggregated patterns across product types, including processing stages, strategic applications, and market concentration. We then analyze results at the individual product level to identify specific patterns for different minerals. Finally, subsection 4.3 presents robustness checks to verify the stability of the main findings across alternative model specifications and outcome variables.

4.1. Aggregate impact of political dissimilarity trade in critical minerals

This subsection examines the overall effect of political alignment with major powers—specifically China and the United States—on bilateral trade flows. The analysis aims to identify whether political proximity plays a systematic role in shaping trade patterns, and

whether this relationship has shifted following the rise in geopolitical tensions after 2016. The results are provided in Table 1.

Table 1: Political dissimilarity and trade - Baseline Specification

	Trade	Trade	Trade
<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{China}	0.00581*** (0.00131)		0.00739*** (0.00156)
<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{China} × Post 2016	-0.00823*** (0.00112)		-0.0114*** (0.00196)
<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{USA}		0.00286* (0.00149)	-0.00250 (0.00167)
<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{USA} × Post 2016		-0.00640*** (0.00109)	0.00388** (0.00192)
Observations	340,831	340,831	340,831

(i) Robust standard errors in parentheses.

(ii) *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

(iii) Political Dissimilarity is measured as the absolute difference in vote similarity scores in the UN.

(iv) All regressions control for exporter-time, importer-time, and pair-fixed effects.

The regression results indicate a statistically significant association between political dissimilarity with China and trade values. Across all model specifications, the coefficient on *Dissimilarity*_{China} is positive and significant at the 1% level (ranging from 0.0058 to 0.0074), suggesting that, prior to 2016, higher political dissimilarity was associated with greater trade flows. However, the interaction term *Dissimilarity*_{China} × Post 2016 is negative and statistically significant in all models, with coefficients between -0.0082 and -0.011. This indicates a structural shift after 2016: while political distance was previously linked to higher trade, this relationship reversed in the post-2016 period, with politically dissimilar countries trading less with China. This shift is consistent with the interpretation that heightened geopolitical tensions, marked by key policy changes around 2017/2018, altered bilateral trade dynamics with China.

The relationship between trade and political dissimilarity with the United States shows a more mixed pattern. Indeed, the coefficient on *Dissimilarity*_{USA} is positive and weakly significant in one specification (0.0029, significant at the 10% level), but negative and not significant in another. The interaction term *Dissimilarity*_{USA} × Post 2016 also shows a negative and highly significant impact on trade in critical minerals. However, when combined with political dissimilarity with China, the interaction of the latter with post-2016 dummy is still negative and significant, but the interaction with US dissimilarity becomes positive and significant at the 5% level. This counter-intuitive result might be due to the colinearity

between dissimilarity with USA and that with China. Indeed, when a country aligns its political position with China, it will probably become politically distant with the USA.

Overall, the results of the individual regressions in columns 1 and 2 highlight the context-specific nature of the relationship between political dissimilarity and trade. The patterns diverge notably between the U.S. and China, particularly in the post-2016 period, indicating that geopolitical factors play an increasingly important and asymmetric role in trade flows for critical minerals. This is in line with the results of Vivoda et al. (2024) who argue that the landscape of trade in critical minerals was characterized by the stratification of nations into “competing groupings”.

This analysis has been conducted at an aggregated level, treating all critical minerals as a single group. However, as discussed in the stylized facts section, product-level characteristics such as processing stage, strategic application, and market concentration may influence how political dissimilarity affects trade. The next subsection presents a disaggregated analysis to assess whether the observed patterns persist across different product categories.

4.2. Political dissimilarity and products heterogeneity

This subsection examines whether the impact of political dissimilarity on trade varies across different classifications of critical minerals. First, we compare processed and semi-processed products to assess whether political sensitivities differ by production stage, based on the hypothesis that semi-processed minerals may be more exposed due to their higher strategic value or the hypothesis that processed minerals may be more sensitive given that most of the processing takes place in China. Second, we group products according to their application in energy and digital technologies to evaluate whether trade in strategically important sectors is more sensitive to political alignment. Finally, we distinguish between products with concentrated and unconcentrated trade patterns to examine whether political dissimilarity with China and the United States has a stronger effect on trade in markets where supply is more dependent on a limited number of partners.

In the classification by processing stage, the results in Table 2 show how political dissimilarity with China and the United States relates to trade in processed and semi-processed critical minerals, with attention to differences before and after 2016. For processed products, political dissimilarity with China is consistently associated with higher trade flows in the pre-2016 period, as indicated by positive and statistically significant coefficients across all specifications. However, the interaction terms with the post-2016 period

are negative in all models but not statistically significant, indicating that while the positive relationship may have weakened, the change is not robust. For dissimilarity with the United States, the pre-2016 coefficients are positive and statistically significant in two of the three specifications, while the interaction terms are small and statistically insignificant, suggesting that the relationship remained broadly stable over time.

Table 2: Political dissimilarity and trade - Level of Processing

	Processed			Semi-processed		
	Trade	Trade	Trade	Trade	Trade	Trade
<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{China}	0.00453*** (0.00174)		0.00399* (0.00219)	0.00550*** (0.00158)		0.00698*** (0.00179)
<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{China} × Post 2016	-0.00103 (0.00156)		-0.00459 (0.00330)	-0.0109*** (0.00132)		-0.0129*** (0.00220)
<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{USA}		0.00729*** (0.00188)	0.00441* (0.00227)		-7.88e-06 (0.00186)	-0.00548*** (0.00202)
<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{USA} × Post 2016		-0.00168 (0.00138)	0.00281 (0.00291)		-0.00775*** (0.00133)	0.00353 (0.00221)
Observations	297,509	297,509	297,509	218,378	218,378	218,378

(i) Robust standard errors in parentheses.

(ii) *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

(iii) Political Dissimilarity is measured as the absolute difference in vote similarity scores in the UN.

(iv) All regressions control for exporter-time, importer-time, and pair-fixed effects.

In contrast, the results for semi-processed products show a different pattern. Political dissimilarity with China is again positively associated with trade before 2016, with significant coefficients across all models. However, the interaction terms are negative and statistically significant, suggesting that this relationship reversed after 2016. For instance, the main effect of 0.007 combined with an interaction term of -0.0129 implies a negative net effect in the post-2016 period. For the United States, the main coefficients are either negative or close to zero and statistically insignificant, but the interaction terms are negative and significant in one specification, indicating a stronger negative relationship with trade after 2016. Overall, these results suggest that trade in semi-processed critical minerals became more sensitive to political alignment in the post-2016 period, particularly in the context of rising geopolitical tensions. This is in line with the fact semi-processed (that include also unprocessed) minerals depend mainly on endowments. Given that the latter are concentrated in a few countries, political alignment should be a key determinant of trade in these minerals. This was clearly the case, for instance, of the US that signed a "memorandum of intent" with Ukraine in 2025 to advance different deals granting Washington access to Kyiv's natural resources and critical minerals. A

similar observations applies to the memorandum of understanding signed between between the EU and the Democratic Republic of the Congo Barsauskaite and Tipping (2025).

Moving to the classification based on energy and digital use, Table 3 presents regression estimates examining the relationship between political dissimilarity and trade in critical minerals, disaggregated by their application in energy and digital technologies. For products used in both energy and digital transitions, political dissimilarity with China is positively and significantly associated with trade before 2016, but the interaction term with the post-2016 period is negative and statistically significant, indicating a reversal of the relationship. This suggests that after 2016, countries that are politically distant from China reduced their imports of these strategically important products. A similar pattern holds for dissimilarity with the United States: the pre-2016 coefficient is positive and significant in one specification, but the interaction term is negative and significant across all models, implying a decline in trade with politically misaligned countries after 2016. This pattern may reflect the heightened strategic and geopolitical sensitivity surrounding critical minerals used in both energy and digital technologies. This includes especially lithium, rare earths and cobalt (Srivastava and Kumar, 2022).

Table 3: Political dissimilarity and trade - Energy and digital needs

	Both energy and digital transition			Either energy or digital transition			Neither energy nor digital transition		
	Trade	Trade	Trade	Trade	Trade	Trade	Trade	Trade	Trade
<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{China}	0.01*** (0.002)		0.007*** (0.002)	0.004* (0.002)		0.006*** (0.002)	0.004 (0.003)		0 (0.004)
<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{China} × Post 2016	-0.014*** (0.001)		-0.008*** (0.003)	-0.001 (0.002)		-0.008** (0.003)	0.007** (0.003)		0 (0.006)
<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{USA}		0.005** (0.002)	0 (0.002)		-0.001 (0.003)	-0.004 (0.003)		0.011*** (0.004)	0.011*** (0.004)
<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{USA} × Post 2016		-0.014*** (0.001)	-0.006** (0.003)		0.001 (0.002)	0.008*** (0.003)		0.005* (0.003)	0.005 (0.006)
Observations	249906	249906	249906	277248	277248	277248	159262	159262	159262

(i) Robust standard errors in parentheses.

(ii) *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

(iii) Political Dissimilarity is measured as the absolute difference in vote similarity scores in the UN.

(iv) All regressions control for exporter-time, importer-time, and pair-fixed effects.

For products used in either energy or digital applications, the results are more mixed. Political dissimilarity with China is associated with higher trade flows before 2016, but the post-2016 interaction terms are negative and statistically significant, indicating a weakening or reversal of this effect. For dissimilarity with the United States, the coefficients are generally small and not statistically significant in either period, suggesting no clear pattern. For products not used in energy or digital technologies, there is no significant relationship between dissimilarity with China and trade in either period. In contrast, political dissimilarity with the United States is positively and significantly associated with trade both before and after 2016.

This suggests that, outside of strategic technology sectors, political alignment with the U.S. was not a necessary condition for maintaining or increasing trade flows, and that trade in these products may be driven more by market or resource considerations than geopolitical alignment.

We now turn to market concentration and examine whether the effect of political dissimilarity on trade volumes differs between products with concentrated and non-concentrated trade patterns. To classify products, we first computed the Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI) for each product using trade data from 1995 to 2022 (see Appendix for details). We then averaged the HHI values over the study period and used the median of these averages as a threshold. Products with an average HHI above the median are classified as concentrated (i.e., traded primarily within a small number markets), while products with an average HHI at or below the median are classified as non-concentrated (i.e., traded across more diversified markets).

Table 4 presents the results. For concentrated products, political dissimilarity with China is positively and significantly associated with trade in the pre-2016 period, but the interaction term with the post-2016 period is negative and statistically significant across specifications. This suggests that while politically distant countries traded more with China before 2016, this pattern reversed following the rise in geopolitical tensions. For dissimilarity with the United States, the pre-2016 coefficient is positive and significant in one model but not robust across specifications. However, the interaction term with the post-2016 period is consistently negative and significant, indicating that trade in concentrated products became more responsive to political alignment with the U.S. after 2016. This is consistent with the idea that countries have become more cautious about relying on politically distant partners for strategically sensitive and supply-concentrated products.

For non-concentrated products, the pattern is more mixed. Political dissimilarity with China is positively associated with trade in all specifications. Yet, the interaction term is negative and statistically significant in column 6. This suggests some weakening of the positive association post-2016, but no consistent reversal. In contrast, dissimilarity with the United States is negatively associated with trade in the pre-2016 period, while the interaction term is positive and statistically significant in all three models. This indicates a clear reversal: before 2016, countries politically distant from the U.S. traded less in non-concentrated products, but this gap narrowed or reversed in the post-2016 period. Overall, the results

Table 4: Political dissimilarity and trade - Level of concentration

	Concentrated			Non-concentrated		
	Trade	Trade	Trade	Trade	Trade	Trade
<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{China}	0.007*** (0.001)		0.008*** (0.002)	0.005* (0.002)		0.008*** (0.003)
<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{China} × Post 2016	-0.011*** (0.001)		-0.011*** (0.002)	-0.002 (0.003)		-0.016*** (0.005)
<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{USA}		0.004*** (0.002)	-0.001 (0.002)		-0.001 (0.003)	-0.008** (0.003)
<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{USA} × Post 2016		-0.01*** (0.001)	0 (0.002)		0.002 (0.002)	0.015*** (0.004)
Observations	329534	329534	329534	174600	174600	174600

(i) Robust standard errors in parentheses.

(ii) *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

(iii) Political Dissimilarity is measured as the absolute difference in vote similarity scores in the UN.

(iv) All regressions control for exporter-time, importer-time, and pair-fixed effects.

suggest that political alignment plays a more consistent and pronounced role in trade for concentrated products, likely due to their higher strategic sensitivity and more limited sourcing options. Mixed findings are found for non-concentrated products that are thus less sensitive to political proximity.

Since the previous analysis shows that the effect of political dissimilarity is heterogeneous between processed and semi-processed commodities, the next step of our analysis focuses on the impact at the individual product level. This approach allows us to capture the specific dynamics of trade for each critical mineral, considering how political alignment with major geopolitical powers might differently affect each commodity. In addition, the demand for different critical minerals is not identical as some of them might be more needed for energy or digital transition than others.

Figure 6 presents the estimated effects of political dissimilarity on trade for individual critical mineral products, focusing on the interaction terms with the post-2016 period. For both China and the United States, the figure displays the ten products with the most negative and the least negative coefficients, meaning that only trade reductions of varying magnitudes are shown. The results reveal substantial heterogeneity in how trade in specific products responds to increased political distance. Products such as cobalt ores (used in lithium-ion batteries, and in the manufacture of magnetic, wear-resistant and high-strength alloys.), arsenic sulfides (used in semiconductor industries), vanadium (steel alloys, for use in space vehicles, nuclear reactors and aircraft carriers), molybdenum (used in making alloys) and inorganic salts (used in construction materials) exhibit strong and statistically significant declines in trade with politically dissimilar partners, suggesting these are particularly sensitive

Figure 6: Coefficients of individual production (interaction terms).

to geopolitical alignment. In contrast, other products, while still negatively affected, show much smaller estimated effects, indicating that trade in these cases may be less constrained by political considerations. This applies to natural graphite (used in thermal management, battery electrodes, and the nuclear industry), manganese ore (used in steel production) and the minerals used in semi-conductors such as silicon, gallium, and aluminium. This variation highlights that the extent to which political dissimilarity affects trade depends on the nature and strategic role of the individual mineral.

Tables A.3 and A.4 in the Appendix provide detailed regression results on the relationship between political dissimilarity and trade at the product level, using HS6 codes to identify individual critical mineral products.¹ The tables report both the baseline effects and post-2016 interaction terms for dissimilarity with China and the United States. The results highlight substantial heterogeneity in the responsiveness of trade flows to political distance across products. For several products—such as cobalt ores, arsenic sulfides, and inorganic compounds—political dissimilarity is associated with significant trade reductions after 2016, particularly in relation to China. In contrast, other products show either weak or statistically insignificant effects, suggesting a limited role for political alignment. These findings support the view that political dissimilarity does not uniformly affect trade in critical minerals, but rather varies with the characteristics and strategic relevance of each product.

4.3. Further analysis and robustness Checks

To complement the baseline analysis focused on political dissimilarity with the United States and China individually, we extend the analysis by examining broader geopolitical alignments. Specifically, we construct measures of political dissimilarity with the Western and Eastern blocs. The Western bloc is defined as the average absolute difference in UN voting similarity between trading partners with the United States, the United Kingdom, and France. The Eastern bloc is defined as the average absolute difference with China and Russia. These variables capture overall political distance from the major powers within each bloc, providing a more comprehensive measure of alignment. The intuition behind this approach is that political proximity or divergence may operate through broader geopolitical alliances, not just bilateral relationships. As a result, countries may adjust trade patterns based on their

¹See Tables A.1 and A.2 in the Appendix for the corresponding product names associated with each HS6 code listed in Tables C and C.

alignment with these blocs, especially in the context of increasing systemic tensions between the East and the West.

Table 4.3 reports the results of the regression analysis using political dissimilarity with the Western and Eastern blocs instead of individual countries. In the pre-2016 period, political dissimilarity with both blocs is positively and significantly associated with trade, indicating that greater political distance did not hinder trade flows. However, the interaction terms with the post-2016 period are negative and statistically significant for both blocs across specifications. This suggests a reversal in the relationship: after 2016, countries politically distant from either bloc experienced a decline in trade. The change is especially pronounced for dissimilarity with the West, with coefficients around -0.008 and -0.004, compared to -0.006 and -0.007 for the East. These results indicate that rising geopolitical polarization has affected trade more broadly, with alignment to either major bloc becoming more relevant in recent years.

Table 5: Political dissimilarity and trade - Political Blocks

	Trade	Trade	Trade
<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{Western}	0.00229 (0.00150)		0.000554 (0.00153)
<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{Western} × Post 2016	-0.00783*** (0.00116)		-0.00408*** (0.00138)
<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{Eastern}		0.00620*** (0.00150)	0.00489*** (0.00160)
<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{Eastern} × Post 2016		-0.0101*** (0.00147)	-0.00672*** (0.00170)
Observations	340,831	340,831	340,831

(i) Robust standard errors in parentheses.

(ii) *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

(iii) Political Dissimilarity is measured as the absolute difference in vote similarity scores in the UN.

(iv) All regressions control for exporter-time, importer-time, and pair-fixed effects.

As a robustness check, Table 6 presents two alternative specifications of the baseline model using the combined dataset. The first two columns use the first difference of the bilateral trade value as the dependent variable. As mentioned in section 3, we take the first difference in order to account for endogeneity. Therefore, by focusing on changes in trade rather than levels, this method isolates the year-to-year variation, which may better capture the short-term response of trade flows to shifts in political dissimilarity. The last two columns of the table use trade volume instead of trade value as the dependent variable. This addresses the possibility that observed effects in the baseline specification could be driven by price changes rather than actual trade

quantities. Therefore, using volume provides an alternative perspective by focusing on the physical flow of goods.

Overall, the findings across both robustness checks are consistent with the main results. The interaction terms for political dissimilarity with China and the United States in the post-2016 period are negative and statistically significant in both specifications. This supports the conclusion that increased political distance, especially after 2016, is associated with reduced trade in critical minerals, and the relationship is robust to different modeling choices and outcome measures.

Table 6: Political dissimilarity and trade - Robustness Checks

	First Diff.		Volume	
	Trade	Trade	Trade	Trade
<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{China}	0.00169 (0.00188)		0.0177*** (0.00247)	
<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{China} × Post 2016	-0.00985** (0.00429)		-0.0113*** (0.00177)	
<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{USA}		-0.00248 (0.00231)		0.0170*** (0.00269)
<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{USA} × Post 2016		-0.00778** (0.00396)		-0.0189*** (0.00208)
Observations	978,384	978,384	337,243	337,243

(i) Robust standard errors in parentheses.

(ii) *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

(iii) Political Dissimilarity is measured as the absolute difference in vote similarity scores in the UN.

(iv) All regressions control for exporter-time, importer-time, and pair-fixed effects.

5. Conclusion

This paper examines the relationship between political dissimilarity and bilateral trade in critical minerals. Using UN voting patterns to measure political distance, the analysis focuses on how alignment or misalignment with China and the United States influences trade flows. The study analyzes overall patterns, then presents a disaggregated approach by examining trade across different product categories based on processing stage, strategic use, and market concentration. It also includes product-level regressions to identify heterogeneous effects across individual minerals and extended the analysis to consider political distance from broader geopolitical blocs. The findings show that political alignment has become a more relevant factor in trade in critical minerals after 2016, a period that coincides with increased geopolitical tensions and changes in trade policy. In the aggregate analysis, there is a shift in the effect of political dissimilarity with China: before 2016, politically distant countries traded more with China, but this pattern reversed after 2016. For the United States, the results are less consistent across specifications, though there is some indication that political proximity has gained importance in recent years.

The disaggregated analysis points to variation in the effects of political dissimilarity across product categories. Trade in semi-processed minerals, minerals used in both energy and digital technologies, and those sourced from concentrated markets appears more sensitive to political alignment after 2016. At the product level, the effects differ across individual minerals, with some—such as cobalt ores and arsenic compounds—showing stronger responses to political distance. This reflects the varying roles that different minerals play in trade. The analysis of broader geopolitical blocs shows that political distance from both Western and Eastern alliances has become more relevant for trade flows. This suggests that geopolitical factors may influence trade not only through bilateral relationships but also through alignment with wider blocs.

From a policy perspective, the findings point to potential vulnerabilities in mineral supply chains that are shaped not only by market forces but also by geopolitical considerations. As countries seek to secure access to critical minerals for the energy transition and technological development, understanding the role of political alignment will be essential in anticipating trade disruptions and designing resilient sourcing strategies. Therefore, trading partners should balance both the economic and political considerations associated with this trade. From the importer's viewpoint, developing and diversifying market supply are crucial to addressing uncertainty given that the demand for such minerals will further increase with energy and

digital transition. Obviously, recycling and a more circular model will be of great relevance. In this line of thought, [Pommeret et al. \(2022\)](#) show that recycling reduces the cost of the transition and that it is crucial to have a sufficient stock of recyclable critical raw materials.

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Online Appendix

A. Critical Minerals Considered and Their Classification

Tables A.1 and A.2 list the HS6 codes and commodity names for the 59 critical mineral commodities analyzed in our study. These tables serve as a clear reference for the mineral classifications based on standard HS6 codes and delineate the scope of the trade data. We further categorize these commodities into three groups. First, by processing level—commodities are classified as either “processed”, indicating a complete transformation into a final marketable product, or “semi-processed”, denoting an intermediate stage of refinement. Second, by application in energy and digital transition—commodities are identified as being used in both sectors, in either one of them, or in neither, which reflects their role in enabling these critical technological and energy-related applications. Third, by trade concentration—using the Herfindahl–Hirschman Index (HHI), we assess whether a commodity’s trade is dominated by a few partners (concentrated) or is more evenly distributed across many, indicating a diversified trade structure. The following subsections detail these criteria and list the commodities included in each group.

To assess trade concentration, we employ the Herfindahl–Hirschman Index (HHI). For each product and for each year from 1995 to 2022, the market share $S_{i,t,e}$ of importer i for exporter e is calculated as

$$S_{i,t,e} = \frac{PrimaryValue_{i,t,e}}{TotalTrade_{t,e}},$$

where $PrimaryValue_{i,t,e}$ is the trade value between exporter e and importer i in year t , and $TotalTrade_{t,e}$ is the total trade value of exporter e that year. The HHI for exporter e in year t is the sum of squared market shares:

$$HHI_{t,e} = \sum_i S_{i,t,e}^2.$$

We then compute the average HHI for each product over the period 1995–2022:

$$\text{Average HHI}_e = \frac{1}{28} \sum_{t=1995}^{2022} HHI_{t,e}.$$

Products with an average HHI above the median value are classified as concentrated (i.e., trade is dominated by a few partners), whereas those with an average HHI at or below the median are classified as non-concentrated, indicating a more diversified trade structure.

No.	HS code	Commodity name	Processed	Semi Processed	Both Energy and Digital	Either Energy or Digital	Neither Energy nor Digital	Concentrated	Unconcentrated
1	250410	Natural graphite in powder or in flakes				✓		✓	
2	250490	Graphite: natural, in other forms, excluding powder or flakes	✓				✓	✓	
3	260200	Manganese ores and concentrates		✓		✓		✓	
4	260300	Copper ores and concentrates		✓	✓			✓	
5	260400	Nickel ores and concentrates		✓	✓			✓	
6	260500	Cobalt ores and concentrates		✓		✓			✓
7	260600	Aluminum ores and concentrates		✓	✓			✓	
8	260700	Lead ores and concentrates		✓	✓			✓	
9	260800	Zinc ores and concentrates		✓	✓			✓	
10	260900	Tin ores and concentrates		✓	✓			✓	
11	261310	Molybdenum ores and concentrates: roasted	✓		✓				✓
12	261390	Molybdenum ores and concentrates: other than roasted		✓			✓	✓	
13	261400	Titanium ores and concentrates		✓		✓		✓	
14	262030	Ash and residues: (not from the manufacture of iron or steel), containing mainly copper		✓			✓	✓	
15	262040	Ash and residues: (not from the manufacture of iron or steel), containing mainly aluminum		✓			✓	✓	
16	280469	Silicon: containing by weight less than 99.99% of silicon	✓		✓			✓	
17	280490	Selenium		✓	✓				✓
18	280530	Rare-earth metals, yttrium, Europium, Dysprosium, praseodymium, Terbium, samarium, neodymium, scandium and yttrium, whether or not intermixed or interalloyed		✓	✓				✓
19	281000	Oxides of boron; boric acids	✓			✓		✓	
20	281520	Potassium hydroxide (caustic potash)	✓		✓			✓	
21	281700	Zinc: oxide and peroxide	✓			✓		✓	
22	281810	Aluminium oxide: artificial corundum	✓		✓			✓	
23	281820	Aluminium oxide: other than artificial corundum	✓				✓	✓	
24	281830	Aluminium hydroxide	✓			✓		✓	
25	281910	Chromium trioxide	✓		✓				✓
26	281990	Chromium oxides and hydroxides: excluding chromium trioxide	✓				✓	✓	
27	282010	Manganese dioxide	✓			✓			✓
28	282090	Manganese oxides: excluding manganese dioxide	✓			✓		✓	
29	282200	Cobalt oxides and hydroxides; commercial cobalt oxides	✓		✓				✓

Note: HS Code denotes the internationally standardized classification of traded products, while Commodity Name lists the official designation of the mineral. The Processed and Semi-Processed columns indicate whether the mineral is fully refined into its final product or remains at an intermediate stage of refinement. The columns for Both Energy and Digital, Either Energy or Digital, and Neither Energy nor Digital specify the commodity's use in energy production and/or digital technologies. Finally, the Concentrated and Unconcentrated columns reflect market structure based on the Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI), indicating whether production is dominated by a few firms or is more fragmented.

Table A.1: Critical Mineral Classification: Processing, Application, and Market Structure (Part one)

HS No. code	Commodity name	Processed	Semi Processed	Both Energy and Digital	Either Energy or Digital	Neither Energy nor Digital	Concentrated	Unconcentrated
30	282300 Titanium oxides	✓			✓		✓	
31	282520 Lithium oxide and hydroxide	✓		✓				✓
32	282530 Vanadium oxides and hydroxides	✓		✓				✓
33	282540 Nickel oxides and hydroxides	✓		✓				✓
34	282550 Copper oxides and hydroxides	✓		✓				✓
35	282560 Germanium oxides and zirconium dioxide	✓		✓				✓
36	282570 Molybdenum oxides and hydroxides	✓		✓				✓
37	282580 Antimony oxides	✓		✓				✓
38	283020 Sulphides: of zinc	✓		✓				✓
39	283030 Cadmium sulphide	✓		✓				✓
40	283322 Sulphates: of aluminium	✓			✓		✓	
41	283324 Sulphates: of nickel	✓			✓			✓
42	283325 Sulphates: of copper	✓			✓		✓	
43	283326 Sulphates: of zinc	✓			✓			✓
44	283691 Lithium carbonates	✓		✓				✓
45	283692 Strontium carbonate	✓		✓				✓
46	284170 Salts: molybdates	✓			✓			✓
47	284610 Cerium compounds	✓		✓				✓
48	284690 Compounds, inorganic or organic, of rare-earth	✓		✓			✓	
49	380110 Artificial graphite (excl. retort graphite, retort carbon and goods of artificial graphite, incl. refractory materials based on artificial graphite)	✓			✓		✓	
50	711011 Platinum unwrought or in powder form		✓		✓			✓
51	711021 Palladium unwrought or in powder form		✓		✓			✓
52	711031 Rhodium unwrought or in powder form		✓		✓			✓
53	711041 Iridium, osmium and ruthenium unwrought or in powder form		✓		✓			✓
54	810191 Tungsten (wolfram) unwrought, including bars&rods		✓		✓		✓	
55	810310 Tantalum unwrought including bars&rods simply s		✓		✓			✓
56	810411 Magnesium unwrought containing by weight at lea		✓		✓			✓
57	811211 Beryllium unwrought: waste and scrap; powders		✓		✓			✓
58	811291 Gallium, hafnium, indium, niobium, rhenium or thall		✓		✓			✓
59	854519 Electrodes of graphite or other carbon, for electrical purposes (excl. those used for furnaces)	✓			✓		✓	

Note: HS Code denotes the internationally standardized classification of traded products, while Commodity Name lists the official designation of the mineral. The Processed and Semi-Processed columns indicate whether the mineral is fully refined into its final product or remains at an intermediate stage of refinement. The columns for Both Energy and Digital, Either Energy or Digital, and Neither Energy nor Digital specify the commodity's use in energy production and/or digital technologies. Finally, the Concentrated and Unconcentrated columns reflect market structure based on the Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI), indicating whether production is dominated by a few firms or is more fragmented.

Table A.2: Critical Mineral Classification: Processing, Application, and Market Structure (Part two)

B. Additional Stylized Facts

Figure A1: Median trade value by political dissimilarity with the Eastern and the Western blocks, before and after 2016

Source: Authors' own elaboration using UNCOMTRADE-BACI and Voeten et al. (2009).

Figure A2: Median trade value over time by political dissimilarity and processing stage for the Eastern and Western blocks

Source: Authors' own elaboration using UNCOMTRADE-BACI and Voeten et al. (2009).

Figure A3: Median trade value over time by political dissimilarity and use in energy and digital applications for the Eastern and Western blocks

Source: Authors' own elaboration using UNCOMTRADE-BACI and Voeten et al. (2009).

Figure A4: Median trade value over time by political dissimilarity and supply concentration for the Eastern and Western blocks

Source: Authors' own elaboration using UNCOMTRADE-BACI and Voeten et al. (2009).

C. Additional Results

Table A.3: Political dissimilarity and trade - Individual products I

	<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{China}		<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{China} × Post 2016		<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{USA}		<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{USA} × Post 2016		
250410	-0.00829***	(0.00242)	-0.00724***	(0.00209)	250410	0.00126	(0.00255)	-0.00713***	(0.00185)
250490	-0.0172***	(0.00513)	-0.000251	(0.00332)	250490	-0.0104*	(0.00598)	0.000767	(0.00330)
260200	0.00164	(0.00256)	-0.00613***	(0.00195)	260200	0.00188	(0.00431)	-0.00217	(0.00250)
260300	0.00100	(0.00276)	-0.0215***	(0.00276)	260300	-0.00979***	(0.00369)	-0.0165***	(0.00294)
260400	0.0660***	(0.0124)	-0.0197**	(0.00834)	260400	0.0412**	(0.0178)	-0.0314***	(0.00946)
260500	0.0248*	(0.0135)	-0.0348**	(0.0158)	260500	-0.0133	(0.0201)	-0.0381***	(0.0145)
260600	0.00891*	(0.00493)	-0.0206***	(0.00688)	260600	-0.00484	(0.00608)	-0.0351***	(0.00533)
260700	0.0182***	(0.00522)	-0.0101***	(0.00383)	260700	0.0166***	(0.00493)	-0.0128***	(0.00381)
260800	0.00288	(0.00369)	-0.0101***	(0.00253)	260800	-0.00286	(0.00317)	-0.00867***	(0.00250)
260900	-0.00144	(0.0126)	-0.0113	(0.0150)	260900	-0.0289	(0.0229)	0.0326*	(0.0178)
261310	0.0276***	(0.00544)	-0.0305***	(0.00464)	261310	0.0242***	(0.00641)	-0.0383***	(0.00441)
261390	0.000781	(0.0113)	0.000243	(0.00698)	261390	0.0128	(0.0114)	-0.00122	(0.00688)
261400	-0.00140	(0.00445)	-0.00692**	(0.00329)	261400	-0.00508	(0.00555)	-0.00224	(0.00353)
262030	0.0153	(0.00978)	0.00791	(0.00966)	262030	0.00381	(0.00787)	0.0143*	(0.00812)
262040	-0.00724	(0.0113)	-0.0142	(0.00879)	262040	0.00833	(0.0117)	-0.0158*	(0.00892)
280469	-0.00482	(0.00421)	-0.00960***	(0.00349)	280469	-0.0116**	(0.00486)	-0.00888**	(0.00360)
280490	0.00629	(0.00489)	-0.00144	(0.00459)	280490	0.00946*	(0.00490)	-0.00164	(0.00411)
280530	-0.00775	(0.00861)	0.0104	(0.00979)	280530	-0.00260	(0.00841)	0.0116	(0.00857)
281000	0.0141***	(0.00354)	-0.00129	(0.00243)	281000	0.0167***	(0.00380)	-0.0106***	(0.00260)
281520	0.00749**	(0.00367)	-0.00932***	(0.00242)	281520	0.000872	(0.00423)	-0.00811***	(0.00249)
281700	0.00438*	(0.00234)	-0.00696***	(0.00178)	281700	-0.000315	(0.00265)	-0.00484***	(0.00172)
281810	-0.00382*	(0.00202)	-0.00484***	(0.00144)	281810	-0.00986***	(0.00223)	-0.00102	(0.00145)
281820	0.00366	(0.00329)	0.0155***	(0.00339)	281820	0.0119***	(0.00391)	0.0115***	(0.00317)
281830	0.00206	(0.00309)	-4.21e-05	(0.00241)	281830	0.00734**	(0.00368)	-0.000488	(0.00244)
281910	0.00573	(0.00351)	0.00344	(0.00255)	281910	0.0156***	(0.00412)	-0.00326	(0.00270)
281990	0.0145***	(0.00455)	-0.00956***	(0.00287)	281990	0.00606	(0.00459)	-0.00761***	(0.00294)
282010	0.00935	(0.00747)	-0.00774	(0.00545)	282010	0.0325***	(0.00819)	-0.0118**	(0.00578)
282090	-0.00175	(0.00372)	-0.00826**	(0.00344)	282090	0.00155	(0.00416)	-0.00954***	(0.00279)

(i) Robust standard errors in parentheses.

(ii) *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

(iii) Political Dissimilarity is measured as the absolute difference in vote similarity scores in the UN.

(iv) All regressions control for exporter-time, importer-time, and pair-fixed effects.

Table A.4: Political dissimilarity and trade - Individual products II

	<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{China}		<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{China} × Post 2016		<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{USA}		<i>Dissimilarity</i> _{USA} × Post 2016		
282200	0.000427	(0.00672)	-0.0107**	(0.00502)	282200	0.0141	(0.00977)	-0.0238***	(0.00570)
282300	-0.000900	(0.00257)	-0.0106***	(0.00207)	282300	-0.00444	(0.00304)	-0.00867***	(0.00204)
282520	0.00346	(0.00554)	0.00179	(0.00388)	282520	-0.00303	(0.00652)	-0.00438	(0.00395)
282530	0.0173**	(0.00850)	-0.0343***	(0.00620)	282530	0.0131	(0.00951)	-0.0361***	(0.00637)
282540	0.000935	(0.00852)	0.0169**	(0.00674)	282540	0.00140	(0.00862)	0.0240***	(0.00633)
282550	0.00611*	(0.00366)	0.00451**	(0.00222)	282550	0.00249	(0.00439)	0.000858	(0.00239)
282560	0.0138***	(0.00415)	-0.00364	(0.00314)	282560	0.0149***	(0.00400)	-0.00576**	(0.00269)
282570	0.00663	(0.00828)	0.0228***	(0.00649)	282570	-0.0116	(0.0106)	0.00148	(0.00696)
282580	0.000472	(0.00340)	-0.00820***	(0.00199)	282580	-0.000517	(0.00316)	-0.00517***	(0.00190)
283322	-0.00465	(0.00343)	0.00521	(0.00322)	283322	0.00215	(0.00419)	0.00299	(0.00275)
283324	0.00488	(0.00631)	-0.0380***	(0.00821)	283324	0.0143**	(0.00720)	-0.0316***	(0.00668)
283325	0.00895**	(0.00380)	0.000878	(0.00274)	283325	0.00699*	(0.00387)	0.00243	(0.00256)
283691	-0.000818	(0.0151)	0.0146**	(0.00637)	283691	-0.0129	(0.00800)	0.0117**	(0.00524)
283692	0.0253***	(0.00649)	-0.0649***	(0.0102)	283692	0.0184***	(0.00684)	-0.0581***	(0.00736)
284170	-0.00832*	(0.00477)	0.00687*	(0.00370)	284170	0.00150	(0.00743)	0.00867**	(0.00410)
284610	-0.00824	(0.00648)	0.0153**	(0.00624)	284610	0.00424	(0.00602)	0.0138**	(0.00646)
284690	0.00666	(0.00481)	-0.00829*	(0.00427)	284690	0.0200***	(0.00526)	-0.0127***	(0.00417)
380110	-0.00523**	(0.00237)	0.000935	(0.00222)	380110	0.00920***	(0.00346)	-0.000939	(0.00225)
711011	0.00885**	(0.00361)	-0.0145***	(0.00508)	711011	-0.000193	(0.00532)	-0.00577	(0.00431)
711021	0.0121***	(0.00339)	0.00700	(0.00537)	711021	-0.0133*	(0.00799)	0.0177***	(0.00475)
711031	-0.0150*	(0.00889)	0.00286	(0.00612)	711031	-0.0472***	(0.00958)	0.0124**	(0.00526)
711041	0.00730	(0.00980)	-0.0245***	(0.00501)	711041	0.000663	(0.0101)	-0.0158***	(0.00403)
810191	-0.00444	(0.00479)	0.00305	(0.00313)	810191	-0.0133***	(0.00489)	-0.00232	(0.00290)
810310	-0.00423	(0.00690)	0.0148***	(0.00273)	810310	0.0132**	(0.00622)	0.00820***	(0.00303)
810411	0.00761*	(0.00431)	0.00512	(0.00373)	810411	0.00496	(0.00434)	0.00287	(0.00359)
811211	-0.0294	(0.0196)	-0.0214**	(0.0103)	811211	-0.0674***	(0.0244)	0.00290	(0.0115)
811291	0.0251***	(0.00484)	-0.00899**	(0.00399)	811291	0.0235***	(0.00415)	-0.0155***	(0.00341)
854519	-0.0193***	(0.00348)	0.0174***	(0.00290)	854519	-0.00374	(0.00374)	0.0188***	(0.00281)

(i) Robust standard errors in parentheses.

(ii) *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

(iii) Political Dissimilarity is measured as the absolute difference in vote similarity scores in the UN.

(iv) All regressions control for exporter-time, importer-time, and pair-fixed effects.